

POULTRY LITTER AS A FEED SUPPLEMENT FOR LIVESTOCK? BACKGROUNDS AND VIEWS OF SOME GHANAIAN LIVESTOCK FARMERS

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ABSTRACT

Cattle, sheep and goats play important role in human development due to good source of protein derived from their meat products. These animals also provide finance, traction power and serve as a hedge against risk in many Sub-Saharan countries including Ghana. The demand for protein from these sources over the years has increased geometrically than the supply as a result of partly low or unavailable feed for these animals. Data on poultry litter was collected from twenty-five livestock farmers who are into sheep, goats and cattle production by simple random selection with structured questionnaire and analysed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 16). It was found out that most of them used cassava husk for feeding their animals and all the 25 (100%) respondents did not know about poultry litter as feed supplement for their animals. Most of them have heard about irradiation as an important tool for decontaminating food products. Logit regression result showed that the number of animals the farmers has affects the decision on the use of irradiated poultry litter as feed. It is recommended that farmers are educated on the benefits of poultry litter as security for them during lean season when there is scarcity of feed.

INTRODUCTION

Protein constitutes an integral part of human development. It can be derived from both plants and animals. When it comes to animals, cattle, sheep and goats cannot be left out. Cattle, sheep and goats, also provide finance, traction power and serve as a hedge against risk in many Sub-Saharan African countries including Ghana. The demand for services and protein from these sources over the years has increased geometrically more than the supply as a result of low or unavailability of feed for these animals. One of the cheapest ways of accessing feed which is high in protein is poultry litter. Poultry litter is a mixture of poultry excreta, spilled feed, and materials used as bedding in poultry operations. Traditionally used as fertilizer but it is now used as livestock feed supplement as a cost-saving measure compared to other feed stock materials. Poultry litter is a low energy feed, similar to average hay in energy value but high in protein and minerals. Though this is known to contain some pathogens, carefully treated litter can be made free of these pathogenic microorganisms which may eventually affect these animals and therefore used successfully as feed supplement for ruminants.

Fig 1 A poultry farm showing birds in a deep litter system

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Chemical composition of poultry litter though varies it is rich in crude protein which could be as high as 31% and thus its utilization as animal feed ingredient, apart from reducing environmental pollution is assumed to have the advantages of providing a low cost feed ingredient according to [1]

A research conducted by [2] on inclusion of different proportions of poultry litter in the rations of yearling Hararghe Highland goats concluded that poultry litter could replace favourably conventional crude protein sources such as noug seed cake by up to 28% in the ration of goats.

The findings from [3] in their research on poultry litter as a source of protein revealed that goats fed on a commercial goat diet gained faster and had greater feed efficiency when compared to the poultry litter-based diet. However, it was observed that goats were sorting the poultry litter-based diet. Feeding ruminants with poultry litter is not only palatable but increases live weight and carcass quality. Beef cattle can consume 3 kg of poultry manure daily, additionally, when fed with 23.5 kg daily of corn silage prepared by adding 30% broiler manure, 1190 g of daily live weight gain can be achieved [4].

The practical potential of ensiling broiler litter with forages or high-moisture grain was demonstrated in several experiments carried out by Virginia scientists [5] and [6] and discovered that broiler litter ensiled with high-moisture (26.3%) maize grain was more palatable, measured by feed intake, and gave better performance than soybean used as protein supplement. Similar results were obtained ensiling broiler litter with forage maize. The palatability, live weight gain and carcass quality of finished cattle fed maize-forage broiler-litter silage were much better than that of cattle fed maize-forage silage plus soybean meal.

It also been found by [7] that partial and total supplementation of forage-maize silage with soybean meal and dried poultry waste was effective, as demonstrated by satisfactory digestibility of nutrients in all groups, either with or without soybean-meal supplementation. An experiments by [8] with a 6-month-old lambs, reported that lambs fed with a mixture of 235 g of poultry litter and 190 g of wheat meal performed as well as those fed with 365 g of wheat meal per day.

Many studies have been carried out on the effect on beef quality when poultry waste is fed to beef cattle for instance [9] and [10] found slightly lower carcass grades, while [11] reported a significant difference in dressing percentages in favour of steers fed poultry litter (control 49.9%; litter (maize cobs) 53.6%, litter (groundnut hulls) 55.6% and litter (rice hulls) 53.0%). Nevertheless, most experiments have not recorded significant differences in the carcass or its quality according to ([12], [13], [14] and [15])

A paper by [16] on poultry litter as cattle feed that, industrial chicken feed (and therefore chicken faeces) contains rendered tissue from ruminants such as cattle and sheep, among other mammals which is commonly used for poultry feed concluded that feeding poultry litter to cattle increases the risk of the cattle becoming infected with mad cow disease (Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy) which devastated the British beef industry in the early 1990s. It is also explained that poultry litter may contain a range of disease-causing bacteria which ruminants can transmit to humans, such as campylobacter, salmonella and E. coli, as well as veterinary drug residues, heavy toxic metals and even rocks, nails and glass

Fig 2 Poulrty litter

Researches done in other places as shown in the literature reviewed meant that poultry litter inclusion in the feed for livestock helps to increase crude protein to some extent despite the potential side effects it can cause. Therefore identifying the costs as well as the benefits derived in monetary terms in order to quantitatively determine its economic importance as feed supplement for sheep, goats and cattle as well as

individual farmers involved in its use is paramount issue to be considered. This is what this piece of research seeks to address.

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Methods

This research employed a structured questionnaire which captures important information on the backgrounds, including age, occupation, marital status, educational levels, number of children their knowledge on feed supplement and the irradiation of poultry litter, the cost of feed in the use of the litter and their general knowledge on irradiated poultry litter as a feed.

Research Setting

The research was supposed to be conducted across large study areas but due to financial constraint it was done in some part of the Greater Accra, Central, Eastern and Volta region of Ghana.

Sampling Technique, Size and Data Collection Method

Data was collected using simple random techniques. Twenty-five (25) of them who have been persistent in animal rearing over the past years were interviewed. These farmers are into animal production such as sheep and goats (Small ruminants) and cattle (Large ruminants). Data was collected by means of structured questionnaire. The Logit regression model was used to establish relationship between the likelihood of irradiation of poultry litter as feed and the various factors affecting it. The decision of a farmer to use irradiated poultry litter is complex situation and can be modeled as two mutually exclusive processes. The first is the decision to adopt the technology and the second the level of intensity or extent of use of that technology, given that adoption has taken place [17], [18] and [19]. This research emphasises is on the likelihood of adoption of the proposed irradiated poultry litter. Theoretically, the Logit model is expressed as:

$$\mu = B_n \sum_1^n X_n + e \text{ Where: } \mu = \text{Likelihood of Adoption,}$$

Adopter is a farmer who answered yes to the question on whether they will use irradiated poultry litter for their animals, B_n = estimated parameters; X_n = Set of independent variables ([19]; [20] and [21]) e = the error term

Hypothesis statements.

The following hypotheses are stated:

H₀: Factor under consideration has no effect on irradiated poultry litter

H_a: Factor under consideration has an effect on irradiated poultry litter

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 16) and Microsoft excel and presented in tables and graphs, percentages and frequencies. Data was gathered on background information such as Age, Sex, Marital status, Number of children, Educational Background, Religion, Occupation, other economic activity, Poultry litter/ feed status including the type of feed, Amount spent on feed, hours animals graze, the animals they own, the number slaughtered, the amount sold, the knowledge about poultry litter, the source of information, whether they have ever used poultry litter, where it was obtained, what they think about the use of poultry litter, what they know about irradiation, their source of information, cost effectiveness of irradiating poultry litter and their view concerning irradiated poultry litter as feed supplement. Also regression analyses was used to ascertain the factors that will contribute to the adoption of irradiated poultry litter with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

Introduction:

This section presents the results from the data collected from the farmers who availed themselves for interaction and interviewed with respect to poultry litter. Their backgrounds and their views on poultry litter have been presented some in charts, others in tables and others in quotations.

District

Twenty-five respondents were interviewed to gather information on what they know about the use of poultry litter as feed supplement 16 (64%) from Ga East District, 4 (26%) Cape Coast Metropolitan Assembly and another 4 (26%) from Akwapim South and 1 (4%) Kpando District See fig. 1 below for detail on the specific areas where data collection was done.

Age, Sex and Marital Status of Respondents

Out of 25 respondents 3 (12%) are 37 years old and another 3 (12%) 43 years old and 2 (8%) 48 years. Others have different ages below 37 years and above 65 years. The mean age of respondents is 44.1 years and Std Dev. 10.6 years. Seventeen (68%) are males and 8 (32%) females with 22(88%) married and 3 (12%) single. Marital status is also known to contribute significantly to the adoption of an innovation because, the couples normally adopt new technology more than an individual (single) person due to the fact that they are more futuristic and think mostly about their children’s well being for the years ahead than the unmarried

Number of Children

On the number of children of the respondents, 6 (24%) have 3, 5 (20%) have 4, another 4 (16%) have 5, 2 (8%) have 1 child, 6 or 7 children while 1 (4%) has 2 or 8 and 2 (8%) have no child. The mean number of children is 4 and Std. dev. of 2. It is known that couples with more children always want to find means of taking care of them for future reasons. That is to care for them during their old ages. They are therefore likely to adopt an invention which positively affects them and their children.

Education, Religion and Occupation of Respondents

Nine (36%) respondents out of the 25 completed JHS, 6 (24%) MLSC, 3 (12%) completed SHS and another 3 (12%) Primary school. Two (8%) attended Tertiary institution, 1 (4%) Arabic school and another 1(4%) had a Non-formal education. Nineteen (76%) are Christians and 6 (24%) Muslims. For their occupations, 24 (96%) are into sheep and goat production with 1 (4%) as a cattle rearer. Apart from these 9 (36%) are into some part time trading, 4 (26%) driving, 3 (12%) masons, 2 (8%) are into other forms of farming. Others are into different outfits such as Security jobs, Hairdressing, Medical Lab job, Plumbing works among others. Religion and occupation correlate somehow especially in African and Asian countries, For example moslems normally embrace sheep, goats and cattle rearing, the situation is not different from Christians however moslems abhor pig production. Though this project is focused on the ruminants, it is worth mentioning since some do not involve themselves directly but employ other people for such jobs.

See figures below.

Type of Feed

As to the type of feed they employ in their animal production, 9 (36%) said cassava husk and free range system, 4 (16%) employ free range system, 3 (12%) grass and cassava husk, with another 3 (12%) who use cassava husk, grass and plantain husk. Other three (12%) also use free range, cassava husk and grass, while 1 (4%) use cassava husk, grass and plantain husk, and a handful also use cassava husk only. In Ghana most small scale production of sheep and goats use household food remnants and cassava husk and plantain to feed their animals. Some also use grass especially those who practice free range system of animal husbandry. More so, the fact that farmers spend about GH¢10.00 per week on feed and also about 8 hours on free range feed hunting show that introducing a feed which cost less and yet with high protein content will be welcome news to them.

Weekly Expenditure on Feed and Number of Hours Animals Graze (Free Range)

Six (24%) spend GH¢10.00 on feed, 2 (8%) GH¢15.00 another 2 (8%) spend GH¢5.00. Fourteen (46%) did not disclose the amount they spend on feed. For those who employ free range system 4 (16%) use 2 hours in doing it, another 4 (16%) use 6 hours and 3 (12%) use 8 , others use similar times

Total Number of Animals, Number Slaughtered and Sold last year

Out of 25 respondents, 3 (12%) have 5, 8 or 13 animals. Two (8%) have 7, 14 or 28 animals while 1 (4%) 3, 9, 10, 16, 20, 23, 37, 54 and 105 animals. Four (16%) slaughtered 1, 2 or 4 animals, 2 (8%) slaughtered 3, 5, and 10 animals, 1 (4%) respondents slaughtered 11 and 3 (12%) did not respond to the question. Four (16%) sold their animal at GH¢ 100.00, another 4 (16%) at GH¢150.00, 3 (12%) GH¢120.00, and another 3 (12%) GH¢130.00 and 2 (8%) sold at GH¢ 60.00 and GH¢ 80.00, 1 (4%) sold his animal for GH¢1000.00 and 6 (24%) did not respond to the question. The fact that some slaughtered some 105 animals means some huge income generation therefore special attention needs to be attached to animal production in these areas

Table 1 Mean, Std. Dev., maximum and minimum values of some variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Weekly feed Expenditure in Cedis	9.30	4.0	2.0	15.0
Number of hours animals graze	4.40	2.50	0.5	8.0
Number of animals	18.0	22.0	3.0	105.0
Number slaughtered	4.0	3.0	1.0	11.0
Amount sold	112.1	29.0	61.0	150.0
Age in years	44.2	10.6	18.0	65.0
Number of children	4.0	2.0	1.0	8.0

Knowledge on Poultry Litter

All the 25 respondents, representing 100% said they do not know anything about poultry litter as far as feed supplement is concerned. Also all the 25 respondents representing 100% said they will go for cheap conventional feed. It is interesting to know that none of the selected farmers heard about poultry litter as a feed. This is not a surprise at all since a crude survey conducted in an environment of scientists only a handful of them know about the litter as feed for animal production. This means that more education should be done on this and research work like this should be published in the national papers and other journal for the end users to apply in their production areas.

What Do You Think About Poultry Litter?

Out of 25 respondents, 9 (36%) said with education they will feed their animals with poultry litter, 6 (24%) said they will like to feed their animals with poultry litter if it will cost less, 4 (16%) will not feed their animals with poultry litter, 2 (8%) said it is not safe for their animals, Others have different views. Though the respondents' do not know about poultry litter as feed some are aware of radiation as an important tool for decontaminating food products. This means it will not be difficult introducing it to their system.

Surprisingly they are ignorant of the fact that poultry litter can be used as feed for their animals upon careful explanation, they agreed that it is comparatively cheaper than the feed they know suggesting that they may go in for it.

Do You Know Irradiation and Where You Heard It?

Out of 25 respondents, 22 (88%) said they do not know about irradiation and 3 (12%) said they know something about it. Two (8%) respondents said they saw it from the internet, 1 (4%) said he heard it from school and 22 (22%) did not respond also, 20 (80%) out of 25 respondents said they will use irradiation for their poultry litter and 5 (20%) said they will not apply it

Do You Agree that Poultry Litter Is Cheap?

Though not yet applied 13 (52%) out of 25 respondents anticipated poultry litter as cheap feed compared to others, 10 (40%) said they don't think it is cheap because the time and inconveniences one has to go through in order to access it and 2 (8%) did not respond, 15 (60%) said they will recommend it to others 6 (24%) said they will not while 4 (16%) said they are thinking about it.

General Comment about Poultry Litter

Most of the respondents were hearing it for the first time. Somebody said "it's a surprise to me", another said it was news to him. Others said they don't know anything about it. One for instance said he needs education on it. One respondent also said he needs education because he doesn't see how poultry litter can be used as feed. Yet others were hopeful that it will be good. For instance, 2 respondents said they will give it a try. One respondent said that due to irradiation he knows that it will be safe for the animals but may be expensive. Another also said he is not sure it will provide a pathogen free supplement and enhance animal's health. Again, one answered that it will help during the dry season. However, others think it will be expensive, one showed the willingness to try even though he thinks it will be expensive. Some respondents answered that they will try it. One respondent said that due to irradiation he knows that it will be safe for the animals but may be expensive. Another also said he is sure it will provide a pathogen free feed supplement and enhance animal's health. Again, one answered that it will help during the dry season. Two did not comment on it at all

The logit regression equation result reveals that only the number of animals the farmers have affects the decision on the use of irradiated poultry litter. The a priori expectation of the regression results was not met. Meaning as the number of the animals increases there is a reduction in the level of acceptance of the use of irradiated poultry litter. The implication to this that, as the farmers' number of animals increases the edge to use more irradiated poultry reduces which implies farmers tend to shun the poultry litter with larger number of animal because of the volume of litter they have carry which in their perception is not an easy task to discharge. See below table for regression results.

Table 8 Logit regression model 1

	B	S.E.	Sig.
Hrs	-0.01	0.666	0.988
An	-0.374	0.22	0.09
Sxd	2.429	3.036	0.424
Msd	-15.93	2.72E+04	1.00
Ag	0.065	0.217	0.764
Dfofr	0.891	4.388	0.839
Dkird	4.226	70.137	0.952
Constant	16.992	2.72E+04	1

Independent Variables: Hrs, An, sxd, msd, Ag, dfofr, dkird Cox & Snell R square = 0.57, Nagelkerker R square = 0.81

Definition of Variables

Dpli = Dummy for poultry litter irradiation, 1 for yes and 0 otherwise as dependent variable

Dkird =Do you know of irradiation dummy, 1 for yes and 0 for no, Hrs = Number of hours animal graze , An = Numbers of animals (shhep, goats and cattle), Sxd = Sex dummy, 1 for male and 0 for female, Msd = Marital status dummy, 1 for married 0 for otherwise, Ag = Age of respondent, Dfofor = Dummy for free

range, 1 for preference, 0 for otherwise, Edudm = Education dummy, 1 for JHS and 0, otherwise as independent variables

Some Points for Discussion

The study shows that the average age of the respondents is 44 years with average number of children 4 means that the future for animal rearing is still bright since relatively young people are engaged in the venture. Though age of farmers is observed not as a determining factor when it comes to adoption of farm inputs and technology, it has been proved by studies ([22] that younger farmers are reported to have a higher likelihood of adopting new technologies due to their longer time horizon ([23] and their zeal to acquire and use farm information ([24] and [25] than older farmers. Older farmers may have more skills in assessing innovation but somehow less inclined to adopt new farm practices than younger ones because they are less receptive to change ([26] Also the fact that most of them have at least JHS and higher education levels show that information dissemination to these farmers will be relatively easier since education has been proved to enhance adoption of innovations and inventions which is contrary to the study done by [27] that, low productivity in Ghana has been attributed partly to low skilled labour force, illiterates and semi-illiterate farmers who have persisted in the use of traditional farm implements and methods in farming. Schooling facilitates learning which creates the enabling mental atmosphere for the acceptance of new practice ([28]. Higher education enhances farmers understanding to follow and use technology earlier than others who are not ([29]

The logistic regression results show that only the number of animals the farmers have is significant factor that affect the adoption of irradiated poultry litter. Factors such as sex, marital status, number of hours of grazing, age as well as education do not that affect the use of irradiated poultry litter. Since the number of animals one possesses is the only significant factor that affect the use of the technology, farmers with large number of animals are encouraged to use it because it is cheaper.

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